

ELECTROMECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF BARIUM TITANATE COATED CARBON FIBERS

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1 Introduction

Multifunctional structural composites are designed to meet multiple performance objectives while minimizing the complexity and weight of the system. This is achieved through the integration of additional functionality to the composite, such as structural health monitoring, [1, 2] actuation, [3, 4] sensing, [5, 6] power generation and storage, [7, 8] ballistic protection, [9] and vibration damping. [10] A specific area of multifunctional composites that has produced increased research interest is the use of multifunctional fiber reinforced composites with piezoelectric functionalities due to the wide application of piezoelectric materials in sensing, actuation and energy harvesting. Previous research has demonstrated devices called piezoelectric fiber composites [PFC], in which the fiber itself is a piezoelectric material. These devices served as sensors and actuators that attached to the surface of structures but did not function as load bearing structural components due to their low strength. In this case, utilizing a stronger core fiber is an effective approach to reduce the weight of the composite and improve the strength as compared to other composite systems. However, the bare fiber does not introduce additional functionalities to the composite except high strength. Therefore, the challenge in this field is adding piezoelectric materials to the fiber while maintaining its strength.

One route in adding piezoelectric behavior to a fiber is to place a piezoelectric material on the surface of the fiber. Coupling the electromechanical response of the piezoelectric material with the strength of the fiber allows for a structural component to have an integrated sensing, actuation, or power harvesting capability. The difficulty lies in producing a conformal coating of the piezoceramic on the

cylindrical fiber without damaging it. Processes such as chemical vapor deposition and pulsed laser deposition have been used to deposit a layer of piezoelectric material on a substrate, but the high temperatures of these processes are detrimental to the strength of fibers that are typically used for structural purposes. [11, 12] Furthermore, typical semiconductor processes can only be applied to the deposition of films on planar surfaces. Therefore, it is paramount to develop processes that maintain the strength of the fibers in order to pave the way for the next generation of multifunctional composites.

Recently, Lin and Sodano developed an active structural fiber composed of a silicon carbide fiber core surrounded by a barium titanate [BaTiO₃] shell. This capacitive fiber had an energy density two orders of magnitude higher than other structural capacitors in the literature based on glass or polymer fiber composites. [13] Therefore, the fiber composite was both multifunctional and outperformed other structural capacitors. Additionally, Lin and Sodano grew BaTiO₃ on silicon carbide fibers and characterized the effective d_{31} coupling coefficient using an atomic force microscope [AFM]. The results showed that the BaTiO₃ achieved an effective coupling coefficient of up to 70% of the value of the active constituent. [14] However, silicon carbide fibers are not the ideal structural component in fiber reinforced composites. A better material is carbon fiber due to its higher tensile strength, smaller diameter and increased flexibility. By using a small diameter fiber, the inclusion of the fiber in a matrix reduces the stress concentration by creating a more homogeneous dispersion of fibers throughout the matrix. Moreover, improved flexibility allows composites of various shapes and curvatures to be created through

conventional fiber layup processes. Additionally, the electrical conductivity of the carbon fiber simplifies the integration into a system by creating an electrode for the piezoelectric coating.

In an effort to utilize the advantages of carbon fiber over silicon carbide, Lin et al. recently developed a two-step hydrothermal method for growing barium strontium titanate [BST] on carbon fiber for use as a capacitor. [15] BST is suitable for capacitor applications due to its high dielectric permittivity; however, it has a low piezoelectric coupling coefficient. In order to make a multifunctional composite that efficiently converts between mechanical and electrical energy, a piezoelectric material with high piezoelectric coupling coefficient is needed. The commonly used piezoelectric material is lead zirconate titanate [PZT] which has a large d_{33} of roughly 600 pm/V, but environmental concerns with lead have created increased research efforts to replace PZT. [16] As an environmentally friendly piezoelectric material alternative, BaTiO₃ also shows a high piezoelectric coupling coefficient [110 pm/V], which can be used to grow on the carbon fiber to create a multifunctional composite with better performance. Common techniques for measuring the piezoelectric coupling coefficients of bulk piezoelectric materials are the Berlincourt method and laser interferometry. [17, 18] These techniques, however, work best when probing flat surfaces that allow for better surface contact or reflection from the surface for the Berlincourt meter and laser interferometry, respectively. Due to the nano-scale dimensions and cylindrical shape of the BaTiO₃ film on carbon fiber, the Berlincourt method and laser interferometry are not viable techniques for accurately measuring the piezoelectric coupling coefficient of the BaTiO₃ film. The miniaturization of piezoelectric materials has made conventional testing techniques obsolete so the development of new techniques is required for continuing progress in the field of multifunctional fibers. Recently, AFM has been widely used in the characterization of nano-scale piezoelectric materials through detecting the sample surface displacement induced by applying an electric field. However, the noise in the measurement induces a large uncertainty in the result. In order to accurately measure the piezoelectric behavior of the BaTiO₃ film on carbon fiber, a refined AFM testing method has been

performed by using the AFM as a sensor and applying a filtering and averaging scheme over numerous cyclic measurements.

In this paper, a novel two-step processing procedure will be used to grow BaTiO₃ films on carbon fiber. Additional functionalities will be added to the composite by utilizing the piezoelectric property of BaTiO₃. This processing technique will be performed at relatively low temperatures in order to maintain the structural integrity of the carbon fiber thus preserving its viability as a structural fiber. The electromechanical coupling coefficient of varying thicknesses of BaTiO₃ coated on carbon fiber will be measured using a refined AFM testing method. This multifunctional fiber will validate the ability to grow BaTiO₃ on carbon fiber while maintaining its strength as well as illustrate an unconventional method for characterizing a piezoelectric material grown on a curved substrate. This research creates a structural fiber that is capable of energy harvesting, sensing, structural health monitoring, and actuation while maintaining the mechanical strength and flexibility of the carbon fiber.

2 Experimental Details

The BaTiO₃ textured film was formed through a two-step hydrothermal reaction. The first step utilized a solution containing a 1:2 volume ratio of titanium tetrachloride [Alfa Aesar, 99.0%] and titanium isopropoxide [Alfa Aesar, VERTEC TIPT, 97+%] in a 1:1 volume ratio of concentrated hydrochloric acid [Fisher, 35%] and DI water. Prior to TiO₂ growth, the carbon fibers [Hexcel IM8] underwent a seeding treatment using a titanium sol-gel containing concentrated hydrochloric acid, isopropanol, and titanium isopropoxide. The solution and carbon fiber tow were placed in a Teflon vessel and encased in a steel enclosure. The solution was heated to between 150 °C and 180 °C for 1 hour to 7 hours to produce a TiO₂ film. This method is described in more detail elsewhere. [19] This TiO₂ film was then converted to BaTiO₃ during a second hydrothermal reaction using an aqueous solution containing a barium source as described elsewhere. [20] This step was carried out at temperatures between 200 °C and 240 °C for 12 hours to 72 hours.

X-ray diffraction [XRD] was performed on the fibers using an X-ray diffractometer equipped with a curved position-sensitive detector [CPS120, Inel] and a CuK_α X-ray tube source. The morphologies of the samples were examined using a scanning electron microscope [SEM, TESCAN VEGA3 LM]. Tensile testing was performed according to ASTM standard C 1557-03 using a table top automated electro-mechanical testing system [Instron 5567]. To determine the effect of processing on the mechanical strength of the fibers, testing was performed on as-received, titanium sol-gel coated, TiO_2 coated, and BaTiO_3 coated carbon fibers. Electromechanical testing was performed in an AFM using an electrically conductive dynamic contact electrostatic force microscopy tip [Park AFM XE-70, DC-EFM]. A lock-in amplifier [Stanford Instruments SR830] was used in conjunction with the AFM. An applied ac signal frequency of 17 kHz was chosen to avoid unnecessary topographic crosstalk near the cantilever resonance.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructure and crystal structure

The TiO_2 growth step produces a textured film consisting of a dense array of aligned rutile TiO_2 nanowires that grow radially from the carbon fiber surface. SEM images of the TiO_2 and BaTiO_3 textured films on carbon fibers are shown in Figure 1. This figure illustrates that the TiO_2 film is initially cracked, but the BaTiO_3 conversion step creates a continuous film with no visible cracks. The BaTiO_3 appears to expand to fill in the cracks due to the conversion mechanism not being solely a diffusion process. It has been suggested that a BaTiO_3 layer is created by the TiO_2 reacting with the Ba^{2+} ions in the reaction solution. This mechanism is, however, detrimental to the creation of more BaTiO_3 because the newly created BaTiO_3 acts as a diffusion barrier for the Ba^{2+} ions. [21] Another suggested mechanism is a dissolution/precipitation description. This states that the TiO_2 is hydrolyzed into either $\text{Ti}(\text{OH})_6^{2-}$ or $\text{Ti}(\text{OH})_4$ and reacts with the Ba^{2+} ions to precipitate BaTiO_3 . [22, 23] The crystal growth continues through a classical diffusion mechanism until the TiO_2 crystal has fully converted. [24] The addition of the larger Ba^{2+} ion increases the volume of the original TiO_2 with its ions having smaller radii as compared to Ba^{2+} [Ba^{2+} 0.149 nm,

Ti^{4+} 0.060 nm, and O^{2-} 0.126nm]. The BaTiO_3 expands into the voids between the array of TiO_2 nanowires. As a result of the small void space between nanowires, the BaTiO_3 grows along the nanowire orientation direction creating a BaTiO_3 textured film. [20] Where there are larger cracks in the TiO_2 film, the BaTiO_3 is able to expand enough to fill in those cracks and create a continuous, crack-free film.

The XRD patterns shown in Figure 2 confirm the growth of rutile TiO_2 through the strong peaks at 27° , 36° and 55° . [25] Due to the amorphous nature of the carbon fiber, a broad peak appears below 30° , but this peak is not profound in the XRD patterns of the coated fibers. The XRD patterns confirm the conversion of TiO_2 to BaTiO_3 because of the characteristic peaks of BaTiO_3 at 32° , 39° and 45° shown in Figure 2. XRD patterns for textured films usually show high intensity, sharp peaks at certain planes, but this is not shown in the resultant sample's XRD pattern. This is due to the radial growth of the textured film around the circumference of the fiber resulting in no net texturing orientation of the film.

Fig. 1 (a) TiO_2 coated carbon fiber (b) Cross section of the TiO_2 film showing the densely packed nanowire growth normal to the carbon fiber surface (c) BaTiO_3 coated carbon fiber (d) Cross section of the BaTiO_3 showing a dense film surrounding the carbon fiber core

Fig. 2 XRD patterns showing the conversion of the TiO_2 to BaTiO_3

3.2 Mechanical and Electromechanical testing

In order to verify that the carbon fiber is not damaged during the hydrothermal process, single fiber tensile tests are performed on the resultant samples [Figure 3]. After the BaTiO_3 conversion process, the fiber maintains 75% of the original tensile strength, keeping an average tensile strength of 4.6 GPa thus allowing it to remain useful as a structural fiber. Additionally, the tensile strength remains higher than the tensile strength of 3.9 GPa for the silicon carbide fibers used in previous research involving BaTiO_3 coated fibers. [14]

The piezoelectric behavior of the BaTiO_3 film coated on carbon fiber is characterized through a refined AFM testing method that measures the sample surface displacement induced by the electric field directly. Individual BaTiO_3 coated fibers are mounted on glass slides which are subsequently attached to conductive AFM pucks. Due to the flexibility of the fibers, the fibers are adhered to a glass slide with the axial direction parallel to the surface of the glass slide. This mounting orientation exposes the surface normal to the axial direction thus probing the displacement response in the same direction as the electric potential is applied. Removing the BaTiO_3 coating from the fiber core using a razor blade allows the carbon fiber to be contacted with silver paint and electrically connected to the AFM puck. This serves as the

bottom electrode during AFM testing. The DC-EFM tip acts as the top electrode. Prior to electromechanical tests, the fibers are poled using a corona discharge technique as described elsewhere. [26] The poling is performed at room temperature with an electric potential of 10 kV for five minutes. This poling technique allows the BaTiO_3 to be poled without the application of a top electrode. Sputtering a gold top electrode over the entire fiber is not desirable in this study because localized actuation at only the AFM tip contact point is required to accurately identify the deformation of the conformal film.

Fig. 3 Tensile tests reveal no change in the tensile strength during the TiO_2 growth, and the BaTiO_3 coated fibers maintain most of their strength after conversion

A 0V to 10V triangle wave at 1 Hz is supplied by a function generator [Agilent, 33210A] and applied to the carbon fiber core while grounding the DC-EFM tip. By applying an external voltage, the mechanical strain response of the BaTiO_3 at the sample surface can be measured by the AFM tip due to the converse piezoelectric effect defined by equation 1

$$\varepsilon_j = d_{ij} * E_i, \quad (1)$$

where ε_j is the strain, d_{ij} is the piezoelectric coupling coefficient, and E_i is the applied electric field. In the case of BaTiO_3 testing, the electric potential is 0V to 10V in the 3-direction with a strain measured in the 3-direction, thus allowing for the calculation of the

effective piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} . The 3-direction is defined as the direction normal to the axial direction. Each sample undergoes at least 50 voltage cycles at various points along the fiber. The noise in the displacement response is reduced by processing the data through a band pass filter. Recording this large number of cycles allows for the reduction of error when averaging the response curves. By plotting the displacement as a function of applied voltage, the slope of the curve gives the effective d_{33} of the BaTiO₃. The displacement versus voltage plot for the BaTiO₃ coated carbon fiber is shown in Figure 4. This plot is typical for all the samples tested. Poling induces domain wall motion and orients the domains in the same direction thus eliminating remnant polarization during the cyclic voltage application. In order to reduce any potential electrostatic forces between the AFM tip and the BaTiO₃, a force of 500nN is held on the tip during testing. Testing a silicon wafer, which is not piezoelectric, shows no displacement response to the applied voltage, thus confirming that the AFM cantilever is not being deflected by the electric field. Therefore, the displacement shown for the BaTiO₃ samples is predominantly from the electromechanical response of the material.

AFM testing results in effective d_{33} values as high as 65 pm/V. Compared to the d_{33} of about 110 pm/V for bulk poled BaTiO₃, the BaTiO₃ film piezoelectric coupling coefficient shows a 65% reduction. [16] This significant reduction can be explained by substrate clamping effects. Clamping effects of a flat substrate have been shown to create a 74% reduction in the piezoelectric coupling coefficient for thick film PZT. [27] Even though the substrate used with the PZT was flat while the substrate in this paper is curved, this still illustrates the large effect substrate clamping can have on the piezoelectric coupling coefficient.

By varying the growth time in the TiO₂ growth step, the aspect ratio (defined as the ratio between BaTiO₃ film thickness and total multifunctional fiber diameter) varied from about 0.45 to 0.6. Challenges in controlling the thickness of the TiO₂ in the initial growth step restrict the aspect ratio to a small range. These dimensions are measured by acquiring SEM images of each tested fiber. Plotting the effective d_{33} as a function of aspect ratio results in scattered data

as shown in Figure 5. Averaging the data produces an average aspect ratio of 0.51 and an effective d_{33} of 34 pm/V. These averages are illustrated on Figure 5 by the crosshairs. A measurable displacement response confirms the conversion of the TiO₂ to BaTiO₃ because TiO₂ is not a piezoelectric material thus eliminating the possibility of it responding to an applied voltage. The response also confirms the creation of BaTiO₃ in the tetragonal phase rather than the cubic phase, since the cubic phase does not exhibit piezoelectric properties while the tetragonal phase does.

Fig. 4 Displacement of the BaTiO₃ and silicon wafer in response to an applied voltage

Fig. 5 The effective d_{33} values from AFM testing with respect to the aspect ratio. The crosshairs show the averages and error bars

4 Conclusions

Textured BaTiO₃ film was successfully grown on carbon fiber by a two-step hydrothermal process. Using these relatively low temperature procedures, BaTiO₃ coated carbon fiber that maintained 75% of its original tensile strength was created, which exceeded the tensile strength of BaTiO₃ coated silicon carbide fibers used in previous research. A refined AFM testing method was developed to measure the effective d_{33} of BaTiO₃ films with low uncertainty. The highest achievable piezoelectric coupling coefficient was 65 pm/V. Varying the thickness of the BaTiO₃ revealed no correlation between the aspect ratio and the effective d_{33} over the thickness range investigated in this paper. This fiber makes it possible to create structural composites of varying shapes that are capable of structural health monitoring, actuation, sensing, and power generation and storage. [14]

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